

NEMATOTOXIC EFFECT OF THREE INDIGENEOUS PLANTS ON LARVAE HATCH OF ROOT-KNOT NEMATODE (*Meloidogyne incognita*)

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ABSTRACT

The research was carried out in the laboratory of the Department of Crop Science, Adamawa State University Mubi (Latitude 10°16"N and Longitude 13°17"E) Nigeria.

Two thousand grammes of each bark of *Eucalyptus camaldulensis*, *Gmelina arborea* and *Cassia siamea* were crushed, blended in an electric Phillips kitchen blender and run at 10,000 rpm for one minutes. To each, six liters of distilled water was added and regarded as standard solution (S). Adding the required amount of distilled water dilutions of S/2, S/10, and S/100 was prepared. Hatching was inhibited to varying degrees when egg masses of root-knot nematodes were introduced in these solutions. Egg-hatch inhibition increases as the concentration of the water-soluble bark extracts decreases. Significantly higher larval hatch of 89% was recorded at the control (distilled water). Though all plants bark extracts recorded low eggs hatch (2% and 4%) at S and S/2, concentration. *Cassia siamea* inhibit more nematodes eggs with 2% hatching at S concentration

KEYWORDS: *C. siamea*, *E.camaldulensis*, *G. arborea*, Nematotoxicity, Hatchitability.

INTRODUCTION

Sasser and Carter (1985) reported over 2,000 plant species as host of *Meloidogyne* species. They parasitize 3,000 wild and cultivated plant species (Baicheva, *et al.*, 2002). Hussey and Janseen (2002) reported *Meloidogyne* species to be of great economic importance and attack more than 2,000 plant species. And that some of the *Meloidogyne* species (*M. incognita*, *M. javanica*, *M. arenaria* and *M. hapla*) are of special economic importance and account for 95% of all root-knot infestation in agricultural lands. *Meloidogyne incognita* (Kofoid and White, 1919) Chitwood, 1994, is a serious parasite of vegetable crops in tropical region. Losses as high as 70% or more have been reported (Chindo and Khan, 1990). In addition to field losses, plants attacked by this nematode become susceptible to root-rot fungi.

Several methods have been employed to manage these pests. The main aim is to improve plant growth as well as crop yield. These can be done by making nematode ineffective or reducing its population below the detrimental levels. Various methods being employed include cultural (crop rotation, dry fallow system, resistant varieties, soil desiccation etc), biological, physical, chemical and plant extracts. Chemical control is the most important and reliable means of controlling a wide variety of nematodes. However, with high prices of nematicides and the pollution it brings to the environment, attention has been directed towards alternative nematode management. The situation necessitates a search for cheaper alternative control measure which can be made available to small scale farmers. One possibility is the use of plants with nematicidal properties.

As a contribution towards the search for alternative control methods, especially the identification of plants extracts for use as nematicides, this study was designed to evaluate three indigenous plants for the effectiveness of their extracts in inhibiting *M. incognita* eggs.

Cassia sieberiana DC is commonly called Gama-fada in Hausa and Ifo or Aridan-tooro in Yoruba. The tree grows up to 15 m in height, with an open rounded crown and the spreading side branches curving downwards. The bark is dark, some times almost black and deeply fissured and yellowish. The wood is resistant to termites and borers, because of this; it is used for Carpentry, while the roots are used as chewing stick in Sierra-leone. The root-bark infusion has been found to be effective in the treatment of Diabetics' patients, Gonorrhoea and expelling Tania (Tape worm). The Mindle in Sierra-Leone used root concoctions as purgative. The roots and

seed extract were also used as fish poison (Irvine, 1961). He also reported that this tree contains *Saponins*, *Anthrquinone glycosides* and *Sennosides A and B*.

Fig.1: Effect of water-soluble bark extract of *Cassia siamiae* on egg hatch of *Meloidogyne incognita* at different concentrations and time. Bars sharing the same letters are not significantly different at $P < 0.05$ according to Duncan's Multiple Range Test. SED (at $P < 0.05$).

Fig.2: Effect of water soluble bark extract of *Gmelina arborea* on egg hatch of *Meloidogyne incognita* at different concentrations and time.

Bars sharing the same letters are not significantly different at $P < 0.05$ according to Duncan's Multiple Range Test. SED (at $P < 0.05$)

Eucalyptus camaldulensis: synonyms: *Eucalyptus rastratus* (Schitd) is of the family Myrtaceae (Bean, 1981; Kelly, 1969). Have common names as Red river gum, Bloodwood, Eucalipto, Eucalyptus Kino etc (Huxley, 1992). Is an ever-green tree growing to 30m by 20m at a fast rate and is a leaf all year, rated 1 out of 5 for usefulness (Huxley, 1992). And that its leaves are a traditional Aboriginal herbal remedy. The essential oil found in the leaves is a powerful antiseptic and is used all over the world for relieving cough and colds, sore throats and other infections (Chevalier, 1996). The leaves contain essential oil 77% of which is Cineol, 5-11% Tannin; the Kino contains 45% Kino tannic acid as Kino red, Glycoside, Catechol and Pyrocatechol (Duke,

1988). He reported the presence of *Cuminal*, *Phellandrene*, *Aromadendren*, *Valerylaldehyde*, *Geraniol*, *Cymene* and *Phellandral*.

Fig.3: Effect of water soluble bark extract of *Eucalyptus camaldulensis* on egg hatch of *Meloidogyne incognita* at different concentrations and time. Bars sharing the same letters are not significantly different at $P < 0.05$ according to Duncan's Multiple Range Test. SED (at $P < 0.05$)

Gmelina arborea Roxb. (Family verbenaceae) is a fast growing tree, frequently planted in plantations to produce wood for light construction, crafts, decoration veneers, pulp, fuel and charcoal (F/FRED, 1994). *Gmelina*

arborea originated in an area of South East Asia from Pakistan and Sirilanka to Myanmar. Widely planted in South East Asian countries including Bangladesh, Myanmar, Thailand, South China, Vietnam, Indonesia, and Philippines (Jensen, 1995). And that it has been less widely planted in Tropical Africa and Latin American countries. In Myanmar, the wood is used for carving images and Canoes, also an excellent wood for Match manufacture, parking cases and ornamental work, also a number of the plant parts have medicinal value and produce good quality honey (Hossain, 1999).

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Collection of Plant Material

The bark of the three plants viz: *Eucalyptus camaldulensis*, *Gmelina arborea* and *Cassia siamea*, were collected from naturally growing trees in Mubi. With the help of a cutlass, the barks of the plants were removed and stored in label polyethylene bags.

Preparation of Bark Extracts

Two kilograms of bark from each of the plant species were crushed into coarse form using mortar and pestle. After crushing the bark for two minutes, 200 ml of distilled water was added. The crush bark was then transferred into an electric Phillips kitchen blender and run at 10,000 rpm for about one minute for proper blending. The blended bark was poured into plastic container and the remaining distilled water was added to make up six liters. The solution was stirred thoroughly with a glass rod, covered and left on the bench for twenty four hours. After twenty four hour, the prepared paste was macerated and filtered through a Whitman No. 1 filter paper. The solution thus collected was left on the laboratory bench for another 24 hours. Suspension was labeled and termed standard solution 'S'. Same procedure was followed to have standard stock solution (S) of all the plants bark extracts.

Preparation of Various Concentrations of the Extracts

Four concentration levels viz: undiluted standard solution 'S', half concentration of the standard solution 'S/2,' obtained by adding equivalent volume of distilled water to each volume of standard stock solutions (S). One tenth of the standard solution "S/10" was obtained by adding ten equivalent volumes of distilled water to each volume of standard stock solution and one hundredth of the solution "S/100", obtained by adding hundred equivalent values of distilled water to each volume of the standard stock solution.

Collection of inoculums:

Root-knot population for the experiment was originated from vegetables fields in Mubi and identified as *Meloidogyne incognita* with the help of perennial patterns as described by Taylor and Nester (1974). Roots were cut into small pieces and eggs were extracted by the method of Hussey and Barker (1973). Eggs were put in sieves lined with tissue paper in order to get freshly hatched juveniles after 48 hours. Nematode population was maintained in a 25 cm diameter clay pots containing steam-sterilized soil.

Experimental Set-Up

Twenty plastic Petri-dishes of 5 mm diameter were used for these studies. These were arranged on the laboratory working table in a completely randomized design (CRD). For each concentration of extract, 10 ml of solution was poured into each of the Petri-dishes using a pipette. At the beginning of each experiment, two freshly removed uniform-sized egg masses were transferred to the solution in each of the Petri-dishes. Equal volume of distilled water poured into similar sized Petri-dishes and inoculated similarly served as control. There were four replicates for each treatment. To prevent bacterial growth, three drops of 1.0% streptomycin sulphate were added to each Petri dish (Hassan *et al.*, 1981). The ambient temperature of the laboratory range from 30-32°C during the course of these studies. The Petri-dishes were kept partly covered to chick loss of water through evaporation. The total number of larvae hatched was recorded at 6,

12, 24, 48 and 72 hours intervals. Hatched larvae were counted under the dissecting microscope.

Statistical Analysis.

Data was statistically analyzed using analysis of Variance (ANOVA). Treatment means were compared following Duncan's multiple range tests (Gomez and Gomez, 1984).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The nematotic effects of Bark water soluble extracts of *Cassia siamea*, *Gmelina arborea* and *Eucalyptus camaldulensis* are shown in figure 1, 2, and 3. The results show that larval hatch commence within three hours of exposure to water extracts of the Bark and distilled water (Control). The results show a decrease in larval

hatch as the concentration of the extracts increases. The increase in exposure period also increase larvae hatch as concentrations of the treatments decreases. Also significantly ($P=0.05$) higher larvae hatch (89%) was recorded at the control than S/100 concentrations of plants extracts. S and S/2 concentrations of the plants extracts inhibit more nematodes eggs with very low hatching. The lowest nematode egg hatch (2%) was recorded at 6 and 12 hours of exposure periods to *Cassia siamea* with little differences of 4% eggs hatch at the same time for *G. arborea* and *E. cameldulensis*. The standard (S) bark extracts of *C. siamea* particularly showed significant reduction in larval hatch throughout the period of observation. Percentage inhibition was 98%. However, more larvae were observed with decrease in the concentration of the extracts especially from six hours of exposure. In all treatments there was a progressive increase in larval hatch as the concentrations of extracts reduced.

The increase in number of juveniles hatched, as concentration decrease may be due to decrease in the concentration of the active principles. Similar observations were made by Padhi *et al* (2000), when they evaluated the nematocidal potential of ten indigenous plant species against *M. incognita*. They reported a reduction in hatching and an increase in nematode mortality in treatments with aqueous leaf extracts of seven plant species. Caudra *et al* (2000), evaluated the nematocidal properties of the by-products from pyroligneous acid, neem (*Azadirachta indica*), Chinaberry (*Melia azaderach*), and *Spirobolus marginatus* and of the colloid compounds of inorganic salts. The greatest percentage of mortality was obtained with neem oil, secretions of *S. marginatus*, and the inorganic compound S-1. Also Jesse (2005), reported the suppression of egg-hatch on root knot nematode with African locust bean (*P. biglobosa*) and Lannea (*L. acida*). The mixture of African locust bean husks and Lannea leaves extracts were most suppressive (9.63%) follow by lannea (10.50%) and the African locust bean (11.56%).

CONCLUSIONS

The results of this study suggest that the plants bark may have nematocidal substances, which inhibit nematode egg hatching. There is need for further work to elucidate the specific active substances (S) for onward transfer to peasant farmers to manage nematodes on their arable lands to increase crop yield.

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